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IOT-based Milk Adulteration Detection System

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ABSTRACT

Now a day's milk is one of the most important food product consumed by people of all age groups and milk adulteration has become a serious problem, where harmful substances like water, starch, detergent, urea and various chemicals are added to increase quality of milk and profit. These adulterants can cause serious health issues. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a fast, reliable and low-cost system to detect milk adulteration.

This paper presents an IoT-based milk adulteration detection system that can monitor the quality of milk in real-time. In this system we are using various sensors to measure parameters such as pH value, clarity of milk, turbidity. These sensors readings are processed using a ESP32 microcontroller and send to a cloud platform through the internet. The collected data can be viewed on a mobile application and on LCD which is interfaced to microcontroller for easy monitoring.

This system helps in quick identification of adulterated milk and reduces the need of complex laboratory testing. It is low-cost, easy to use, and suitable for households, dairy farms, and milk collection centres.

Keywords:- Internet of Things (IoT), Smart Sensors, Real-Time Monitoring, Cloud Computing

INTRODUCTION

In our day to day life milk is one of the widely consumed and nutritionally important. It is a rich source of proteins, vitamins, minerals, etc. In India dairy production is one of the largest agricultural sector, maintaining milk quality is most important for public health and economic stability. However, milk adulteration has become a serious problem in recent years.

With help of advance technology, the Internet of Things (IoT) has known as a powerful tool for smart monitoring and automation. IoT enables interfaced devices and sensors to collect data, process it and transmit over the internet in real time. By interfacing sensors with microcontroller and cloud platform, it becomes easy to continuously monitor the quality parameters of milk.

This paper presents an IoT-based milk adulteration detection system that provides real-time monitoring and analysis of milk quality. This system aims to offer a low-cost, user-friendly solution, for dairy farmers and consumers. This system helps to improve food safety, enhance quality control and protect consumer health.

LITERATURE SURVEY/REVIEW

Now a day's milk adulteration is very serious problem. Milk adulteration is widely studied due to it has impact on public health, food safety and dairy industry economics.

Researches have explored many methods for detecting adulterants using various microcontrollers. In this project we used ESP32 microcontroller because it is low cost, powerful and widely used in IoT projects.

The paper [1] published by Prof. Prachi A Deshpande and paper [2] published by Dr.P.Ganesh Kumar focuses on build a system for monitoring quality of milk using sensors and IoT technology using Arduino and sensors such as temperature sensor, colour sensor. The paper [3] published by Auldist,M.J.;Hubble,I.B gives how mastitis (infection in cows) affects the quality of milk. This explains that infected milk shows changes in parameters using sensors of milk such as fat, protein and somatic cell count.

The paper [4] published by Barbano, D.M.;Y.Ma;Santos,M.V explains the quality of raw milk can be affected the shelf life of processed milk. The paper [5] published by Dekkers,J.C.M.; VanErp,T.;Schukken,Y.H focuses on reducing somatic cell count and improve milk quality and increases profit for dairy farmers.

Using sensors, we can count the cells in the milk. If cell count is low in the milk then the milk price is better and it improves product quality.

METHODOLOGY

Block Diagram:

The System Architecture includes the hardware Components: ESP32 microcontroller, pH sensor, MQ sensor, Turbidity sensor, LCD. The methodology consist of requirement analysis, hardware design, software development, testing.

1) **MQ Sensor:**

This sensor uses the absorption of infrared light at a specific frequency to monitor and identify amount of carbon dioxide. This sensor runs on 5V DC and consumes around 800mW. It detects Hydrogen, Carbon Monoxide, LPG, Methane, Alcohol, Smoke and Propane.

2) **pH Sensor:**

pH sensor detects acidity and alkalinity levels in water and other various liquids. This sensor works by measuring voltage differences between a special glass measuring electrode and stable references electrode, which connected to meter then it converted into a pH value on a scale of 0 to 14.

3) **Turbidity Sensor:**

Turbidity sensor detects the cloudiness and clarity of water and milk due to suspended particles. This sensor uses a light emitter and photodiode. The sensor

measured in NTU units and gives output in analog or digital form.

Initially detailed study was conducted to identify common milk adulterants such as water, urea, starch, detergent, etc. Then suitable sensors are selected including a pH sensor, turbidity sensor and MQ gas sensor. These sensors measures acidity, alkalinity, clarity and presence of harmful gases or chemicals in milk.

The system architecture is designed by using ESP32 microcontroller as the central processing unit. Then the sensors are interfaced with the ESP 32, which collects analog data and convert it into digital data. The measured data is continuously compared with standard milk quality values to determine the adulteration of milk.

In IoT implementation, the ESP32 with Wi-Fi capability is used to transmit data to a cloud platform. The data is stored and monitored through an application. If any parameter is larger than standard milk parameter, an alert notification is send to user.

The development includes hardware integration, coding using Arduino IDE and cloud configuration. Testing done by in real-time sample testing with pure and adulterated milk samples. This methodology ensures low-cost implementation, easy to use and efficient detection of milk adulteration.

CONTENT

This project mainly focuses on developing a smart and reliable system for detecting impurity in milk using sensors and cloud connectivity. Milk adulteration is a major issue in dairy industry, affecting consumer health and product quality. Traditional testing methods are time consuming and it requires laboratory analysis, which makes

real-time monitoring very difficult. This system interfaces pH sensor, turbidity sensor, and MQ gas sensor with a ESP32 microcontroller. Sensors collect the data and processed by microcontroller and transmitted to a cloud platform using IoT technology. The system monitors real-time data and sends alerts when abnormal values detected.

This project ensures improved food safety transparency in dairy farms, and quick detection of adulterants like water, detergent, urea, starch and chemicals. This system is cost-effective, portable and suitable for dairy farms, milk collection centres and quality control laboratories.

Table 1:-Focus and Scope of the project

Focus	Scope
IoT Based Milk Quality Monitoring	Real-time milk adulteration detection
Sensor-Based Detection	Detection of pH, turbidity, gas and chemicals
Food Safety Technology	Prevention of harmful milk consumption
Cloud Integration	Remote monitoring through mobile application

RESEARCH AND REVIEWS

Recent research gives sensor based and using IoT milk adulteration detection system. These researches have used various sensors to detect physical and chemical changes in the milk. Several researches use the microcontroller like Arduino and NodeMCU for processing data and transmitting over the internet.

For improving detection accuracy machine learning technique is also used. By monitoring sensory data patterns, code can classify pure and adulterated milk with higher precision. Some researchers also focus on portable devices and making this system user friendly and low-cost.

However, some challenges remain in terms of accuracy, environmental

variations, sensitivity of sensor, detection of very small quantity of adulterants. Overall, this system represents approach towards ensuring milk quality, enhancing food safety and protect health of consumer.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The development of IoT-based milk adulteration detection system was successfully implemented and tested with pure milk and adulterated milk with various adulterants. These system measures parameters accurately such as pH value, turbidity, any gas is present using corresponding sensors.

Experimental results shows that, when testing of 6 samples of milk the pH sensor measures pH of pure milk and

adulterated milk caused by adulterants, the turbidity sensor measures clarity of pure milk and adulterated milk, the MQ sensor measures any gas or chemical is present in the pure milk and adulterated milk, then this real-time data was transmitted to the cloud platform using

IoT. The accuracy of detection of the system was found to be satisfactory for small-scale dairy applications. The results confirmed that this system can distinguish between pure and adulterated milk in real-time.

Different samples of milk	pH value	ppm value	NTU	Adulterated/Non-Adulterated
Pure milk	6.58	1115	12	Non- Adulterated
Chalk Powder	10.1	797.14	45	Adulterated
Milk Powder	6.59	1186.24	18	Adulterated
Milk Powder+Urea	9.5	650	52	Adulterated
Salt + Sugar + Urea	10.6	1180	60	Adulterated
Processed Milk + Urea	9.9	916	48	Adulterated

DISCUSSION

The integration of these sensors improves the reliability and accuracy of adulteration detection compared to single-parameter testing methods. This sensor fusion helped in identifying different types of adulterants based on parameters.

Some challenges were observed:

- 1) Sensor calibration is required for maintain accuracy.
- 2) Various environmental factors such as temperature.
- 3) Detection of very small quantities of adulterants.

Despite these limitations, this system demonstrates a low-cost, portable and real-time solution for monitor quality of milk. This system can be effectively used in dairy farms, milk collection centres and households to ensure food safety and

prevent health risks. This implementation proves that the IoT technology can be improved transparency, quality control and consumer confidence in dairy supply chains.

CONCLUSION

The IoT based milk adulteration detection system successfully designed and implemented to monitoring milk quality in real-time. By interfacing multiple sensors with IoT technology, this system can detect adulterants like water, urea, starch, detergent, chemical and gas by providing instant alerts and monitoring through a cloud platform.

Overall, this system is low-cost, user friendly, portable and suitable for dairy farms, milk collection centres and households. This helps in ensuring milk quality, food safety, protecting health of consumer.

FUTURE SCOPE

In future the system can be improved by using advanced sensor integration in this more sensitive and specialized sensor are used to detect a wider range of chemical adulterants, machine learning implementation in this AI/ML algorithms can be used to improve accuracy and automatically classification of different types of adulterants, mobile application development in this we can create a dedicated mobile app for better user interface, cloud data analysis in this we can implement big data analytics for large-scale dairy monitoring, automatic report generation in this it can create digital quality certificate for milk suppliers.

With above implementations the system can become a smart, intelligent and automated milk quality monitoring solution in future.

REFERENCES

1. Swastik Vaidya, Prof. Prachi A Deshpande. International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology [1-9] (2025).
2. Dr. P. Ganesh Kumar. A. Alagammai, B.S. Madhumitha. IoT based Milk Monitoring system [6-9] (2022).
3. Auldish, M. J.;Hubble,I.B.. Effects of mastitis on raw milk and dairy products. Australian Journal of Dairy Technology [3-6] (1998).
4. Barbano, D. M.;Y.Ma;Santos,M.V.. Influence of raw milk quality on fluid milk shelf life. Journal of Dairy Science 89(sup.) [1-9](2006).
5. Dekkers, J.C.M.; Van Erp,T.; Schukken, Y.H.. Economic benefits of reducing somatic cell count under the milk quality program of Ontario. Journal of dairy Science 79:396-401[16](1996).
6. Azad and Ahmed.Common milk adulteration and their detection techniques [1-4] (2016).